

AHP 65 features articles about Mongghul (Tu) agricultural transitions, a 'big' Reb gong incense offering, the Ganden offering of the 25th day in Reb gong, a case study of Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan, and Tibetan female workers; a policy brief on promoting equitable and quality compulsory education in China; a critical literature review of human capital theory and occupational realities of college graduates from Dzorge County, China; film and audio alerts; original short stories; memories; and a book review.

Articles, Alerts, Literature, Memories, Reviews 2025

Articles, Alerts, Literature, Memories, Reviews

Asian Highlands

Perspectives 65

2025

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FILM AND AUDIO ALERTS

DON RIN NYIN རོན་རིན་ཉིན་ TIBETAN
VILLAGE'S *LAB TSE* RITUAL¹
Bde skyid sgrol ma བདེ་སྐྱིད་སྐྱོད་མཁའ་མ། (Dejizhuoma 德吉卓玛)

39 minutes 3 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14591942>

Don rin nyin Village is located in Nya lung Town, Reb gong (Tongren) County, Rma lho (Huangnan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, in the eastern part of Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Elders say our village is in a valley shaped like a sitting elephant, and we reside on its head: *don* 'ultimate truth', *rin* 'treasure', and *nyin* 'sunny side'. Together, these terms convey the idea of the true treasure of an elephant on the sunny side of a valley.

There are around forty-three families in my home community. The seventeenth day of the sixth lunar month annually is a very auspicious day for our village. We hold a *lab tse* ritual and offer incense, insert *mda' shing* in the *lab tse*, and place *gher* 'treasure' to our mountain deity, A mye brag skya, on Mount Dpal ri 'Peaceful Deity' to increase our livestock and protect villagers. It takes thirty minutes to two hours to reach Dpal ri Mountain from our village. According to village elders and family members, only men went to Dpal ri Mountain to celebrate our mountain deity before 1958. After monasteries reopened in the 1980s, it was decided that elders, men, women, and children would all go to Mount Dpal ri to attend the *lab tse* ritual and picnic there.

We prepare various items as the ritual day approaches, including *gher*, *dmu thag*, *sher rtsig*, *rlung rta*, *mda' shing*, *bsang* 'incense', milk, *rtsam pa*, yogurt, liquor, yak dung fuel, water, pots, bowls, ladles, bread, butter, and tea bricks.

¹ Bde skyid sgrol ma བདེ་སྐྱིད་སྐྱོད་མཁའ་མ། (Dejizhuoma 德吉卓玛). 2025. Don rin nyin རོན་རིན་ཉིན་ Tibetan Village's *Lab tse* Ritual. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:248-251.

Every household gets up early on the ritual day. After washing, people wear their most beautiful Tibetan robes and new clothes. They put bread, *rtsam pa*, milk, yogurt, and other food in bags and carry them on their backs. Some people ride motorcycles while others walk to Mount Dpal ri. After reaching Mount Dpal ri, each household piles its things together. Women make a hearth with three big stones, put a big pot on the stones, and make a fire.

Water, brick tea, and milk are added to the pot, and milk tea is boiled. Since it is for offering to the mountain deity, milk from each household is poured into the pot. After the tea boils, *gher* is positioned, and participants offer incense. Next, *mda' shing* are inserted and *sher rtsig* is offered.

People, including some women, take *rtse brgya* and circumambulate the *lab tse* while chanting *ma Ni*. They give *rtse brgya* to men who are inserting *mda' shing*. Women also circumambulate and chant *ma Ni*. Men use *dmu thag* to tie the *mda' shing* and then use long silk to wrap the bottom of the *mda' shing*.

Next, milk tea is boiled. After drinking some, participants sit in a circle, put *rtsam pa*, butter, fruit, and snacks in the center among the villagers. Then eating begins. Some people perform *skor bro* 'circle dance' and sing. After eating, women go to Gnas mdum beneath the *lab tse*.

Elders describe a practitioner, Bse kyi rgyal ba byang chub bron, from our village who meditated on Mount Skya rgan grub gnas for many years. One day, he could fly and flew to Mount Dpal ri where we hold the *lab tse* ritual. Locals named the place Gnas mdum, also known as Sgrub gnas byang chub phug. He continued to meditate at Gnas mdum. During the *lab tse* ritual, village women offer incense, chant *ma Ni*, and place *gter* to remember Bse kyi rgyal ba byang chub. Women then collect their things and return home.

TIBETAN TERMS

bzang drug བཟང་ལྗུག་, purification powder

bsang བསང་།, incense

bsang khug བསང་ཁུག་, incense bag

dmu thag དམུ་ཐག་, Locally, the *dmu thag* symbolizes the ladder to the sky (grasp it to ascend to Heaven). Additionally, people believe that if the *dmu thag* is wound around the *lab tse*, it has power that remains untethered for a long time.

don ryi nyin དོན་རྟི་ལྷིན་, Anin འཁོ་ཡི་, The Tibetan village where the video was made.

gnas mdum, གནས་མདུན་, name of a place below the *lab tse*

go rti'i rgyal bo, གོ་རྟི་འི་རྒྱལ་བོ་, diamond-shaped bread as big as two palms. Such bread is offered as incense and with *gter*.

gter khung, གཏེར་ཁུང་།, treasure hole

lab tse, lab tse ལའ་ཚེ།, are where mountain deities dwell. *Lab tse* are constructed with wooden poles resembling arrows, sheep wool thread, stones, and prayer flags, suggesting presenting weapons to the mountain deities. Locally, *lab tse* are atop mountains and renewed yearly to receive protection from mountain deities.

mda' shing, མདའ་ཤིང་།, wooden poles resembling arrows. Some *mda' shing* tops resemble arrows. Some resemble spears, swords, and guns. *Mda'shing* are not colored in Don ryi nyin Village. *Mda' shing* suggest a close relationship with the mountain deity and a state of peace and non-violence. Wooden arrows decorated with the color of blood imply that the mountain deity is more violent.

mdong mo མདོང་མོ།, diamond-shaped bread as big as two palms. Such bread is offered as incense and with *gter*.

rlung rta, རླུང་རྟ།, Rectangular pieces of paper with specific elements in fixed positions, e.g., a Garuda on the top right, a dragon on the top left, a horse in the center, a lion on the bottom right, and a tiger on the bottom left. *Rlung rta* bring good fortune to villagers and protect them.

rtsam pa, རྩམ་པ།, roasted barley flour

rtse brgya, རེ་བརྒྱ།, Birch branches are tied with sheep wool and offered to the mountain deity because the birch tree has beautiful branches and is not poisonous.

sgrub gnas byang chub phug, སྐྱུབ་གནས་བྱང་ཚུབ་ཕུག།, alternative name for Gnas mdum

sher rsig, ཤེར་རྩིག།, Wheat grain is stirred as it is roasted. Some wheat grain turns black after being roasted, while others do not. The grains of two colors are mixed. Black represents yaks, and white represents sheep. The more grain provided, the better the growth of your livestock will be in the next year.

spen ma, སྤེན་མ།, tamarisk

tsha gsur, ཚ་གསུང།, offering made by roasting a mixture of *rtsam pa* with the three whites (milk, yogurt, butter).

COLLECTING YAK HAIR IN YUL SHUL
TIBETAN AUTONOMOUS PREFECTURE,
MTSHO SNGON (QINGHAI) PROVINCE,
PR CHINA¹

Bkra shis rab rgyas བཏཱ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ། (Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰)

1 minute 23 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14299307>

Filmed in Thang skyid Village, 'Ba' dgon Township, Chu dmar leb County, Yul shul Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China by Bkra shis rab rgyas on 6 June 2024.

Local Tibetans collect yak hair and wool and castrate three-year-old yaks in this community annually during the sixth lunar month. This time is chosen because it coincides with the caterpillar fungi collection season. Many people come to gather caterpillar fungi and help pastoral families with yak hair collection. During yak hair collection, each family gathers wool and cuts the hair of fifty to seventy yaks. However, female yaks over three years old do not have their hair cut or wool collected. Twenty to thirty people typically help each family during yak hair collection.

Historically, tents, bags, slingshots, quilts, ties for yaks, yak hair strings, and even eye protectors were made from yak hair. In 2024, life had changed and hair was collected from two or three older yaks. There was no longer a need to make many items from yak hair. In 2024, yak hair was used to make and sell

¹ Bkra shis rab rgyas བཏཱ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ། (Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰). 2025. Collecting Yak Hair in Yul shul Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:252-253.

ties for yaks. If outsiders came to buy, the price for yak hair was sixty-two RMB per kilogram.

TIBETAN TERMS

'ba' dgon འབའ་དགོན།

bkra shis rab rgyas བཀྲ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ།

chu dmar leb རྩ་དམར་ལེབ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྒོན།

thang skyid ཐང་སྐྱིད།

yul shul ཡུལ་ཤུལ།

CHINESE TERMS

Qinghai 青海

Renminbi, RMB 人民币

Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰

AN A MDO TIBETAN PASTORAL FAMILY'S ONE MILLION WATER OFFERING¹

Bkra shis rgya mtsho བླ་ཤེས་རྒྱ་མཚོ། (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13924945>

13 min 51 sec

Filmed with an iPhone 12 Pro Max

Flutist: Lab sgron rgyal

Date: 4 August 2024

A Tibetan herding family's water offering ritual at Yen dar in Rka rgan Valley, Thang mgo (Tanggu) Town, 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China is documented. The specific location is at a latitude of 34°59'10", longitude of 100°46'42", and an elevation of 3,766 meters above sea level.

On the morning of 3 August 2024, I drove with my nephew, Bsod nams bkra shis (b. 2014); niece, A+yon chos sgron (b. 2018), and sister-in-law Nyi ma lha mo (b. 1996) to visit the family of my maternal uncle, Ngag dbang smin grol (b. 1965). We traveled to our family pasture, Yen dar, in Rka rgan Valley, which my maternal uncle's family was using for summer grazing.

The journey from the county town to the pasture was approximately forty kilometers and took about half an hour due to the rough road through our community pasture.

Recently, my family relocated to 'Ba' rdzong County Town, and my maternal uncle's family now uses our land, paying us 40,000 RMB annually. My visit was to assist with a water offering and document it on video.

¹ Bkra shis rgya mtsho བླ་ཤེས་རྒྱ་མཚོ། (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措). 2025. An A mdo Tibetan Pastoral Family's One Million Water Offering. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:254-256.

Water offerings are an important and growing social trend in our community. Traditionally, families have offered water daily to Buddhist images and statues in their shrine rooms. With increased access to information, many now emulate this practice, motivated by a Buddhist belief that offering water increases virtue. The eleventh-century Buddhist master, Atisha (982-1054), advised Tibetans that offering clear water helped accumulate merit. This practice is now widespread in Tibetan monasteries and by individual families.

I interviewed my aunt, Skal bzang sgrol ma (b. 1970), who explained that the ritual began locally in about 1994 with offerings for the healthy birth of her family's eldest son, Yum skyabs rgya (b. 2016), and to increase family merit. Initially, we aimed to offer one million water offerings, and for that aim we offer around 100,000 each summer. We have since made offerings for the second son, Tshe dpal mkhar (b. 2018), the second daughter-in-law Choe bzang sgrol ma (b. 1996), and their sons, Sras mchog rgya (b. 2022) and Phur ba skyabs (b. 2024). Unfortunately, we couldn't complete the 100,000 water offerings in 2022 because my third nephew was born that year and was ill for several years. Only recently have we been able to relax and see him in better health. We need to complete more than 100,000 offerings to reach our goal by the summer of 2025. Although we hoped to finish in the summer of 2024, the task is not easy. so we expect to accomplish it next summer.

The offering involves scattering a *bzang drug* (six precious substances: amomum tsaoko, bamboo manna, clove, saffron, nutmeg, and *Elettaria cardamom*) powder in water in a large plastic container. On the first day, this water is offered in front of an image of Buddha Amitabha near the water offering location. The following day, the local incarnation of Buddha's image replaces Buddha's picture

During the ritual, a statue of Dzam b+ha la 'God of Wealth' is placed in a bowl on a metal folding bed at the end of a line of seven bowls. The God of Wealth and the line of seven bowls remain stationary until time to take a break. Extra bowls

are used repeatedly during the offering. A single string of beads with 108 beads is also placed on the bed. After completing one round, a bead is moved to the side to keep count of the numbers.

Four people are involved in the process. Two pour water into the offering bowls, one transfers water from the bowls into another container, and a fourth adds a small amount of water to ensure the bowls are thoroughly rinsed.

On 3 August 2024, 5,000 bowls of water were offered in the morning and 2,000 more after lunch. On 4 August 2024, 3,000 offerings were made, totaling 10,000 over these two days. My aunt's younger sister's two daughters joined us until noon because that family is my uncle's neighbor. We shared a meal under sun shades on the grassland outside the tent.

TIBETAN TERMS

a+yon chos sgron ཨྲན་ཚོས་སྒྲོན།

bsod nams bkra shis བསོད་ནམས་བརྒྱ་ཤིས།

choe bzang sgrol ma ཚོས་བཟང་སྒྲོལ་མ།

lab sgron rgyal ལབ་སྒྲོན་རྒྱལ།

nyi ma lha mo ཉི་མ་ལྷ་མོ།

rka rgan ཀ་རྒྱན།

sras mchog rgya སྤར་བ་སྐྱབས།

yen dar ཡེན་དར།

bkra shis rgya mtsho

བརྒྱ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

bzang drug བཟང་དུག

dzam b+ha la རྩམ་བླ་ལ།

ngag dbang smin grol

ངག་དབང་སླེན་གྲོལ།

phur ba skyabs ཤུམ་མཚོག་རྒྱ།

skal bzang sgrol ma

སྐལ་བཟང་སྒྲོལ་མ།

tshe dpal mkhar ཚེ་དཔལ་མཁའ།

yum skyabs rgya ཡུམ་སྐྱབས་རྒྱ།

CHINESE TERMS

Hainan 海南

Tanggu 唐谷

Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措

Qinghai 青海

Tongde 同德

YAK LIVES ON THE MOUNTAINS

Bkra shis rab rgyas བཀ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ། (Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰)¹

6 minutes 59 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13280854>

Filmed by Bkra shis rab rgyas, 7 July 2024, in Thang skyid Village, 'Ba' dgon Township, Chu dmar leb County, Yul shul Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. This film showcases female and male yaks and their lives in the mountains throughout the four seasons, highlighting the diverse landscape.

TIBETAN TERMS

'ba' dgon འབའ་དགོན།

bkra shis rab rgyas བཀ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ།

chu dmar leb རྒྱ་དམར་ལེབ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།

yul shul ཡུལ་ཤུལ།

CHINESE TERMS

Qinghai 青海

Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰

¹ Bkra shis rab rgyas བཀ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ། (Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰). 2025. Yak Lives on the Mountains. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:257.

TIBETAN *SRUNG RTAGS* AND YAK
PARASITE TREATMENT¹

Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措)

9 minutes 45 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11103546>

This film was made in Sha rgya Community, Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. I recorded my maternal grandmother (Dkar mo rgyal, b. 1937) and my mother (Rgya kho, b. 1964) making *srung rtags* 'protective clothing labels from wool and cloth' using my iPhone 12 on Friday, March 1, 2024. Grandmother explained that the wool must be greased because grease symbolizes wealth and merit.

We perform the *Srung rtags* ritual once a year in our home in Sha rgya Community, usually on the first, third, or fifteenth days of the Lunar New Year. These days are considered auspicious. The ritual aims to eliminate all distractions and obstacles to complete what is desired as soon as possible.

On the first day, Grandmother and Mother made six *srung rtags* for six different yaks belonging to guardian deities: Dpa' ldan lha mo, Yul lha, A myes dam chen mgar ba nag po, A myes glang chen, A myes rma chen, and Sman chu'i a ma lab sgron ma, which took twenty minutes. Mother mentioned that she did not want to make *srung rtags* for Dpa' ldan lha mo, a female guardian deity, because one yak that had belonged to her had died suddenly. Grandmother believed this was because the deity was unhappy. Grandmother said a *bla ma* said that ten

¹ Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措). 2025. Tibetan *Srung rtags* and Yak Parasite Treatment. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:258-260.

of our yaks died in 2023 because Dpa' ldan lha mo was unhappy, so this year, we needed to offer her more incense to make her happy.

On Saturday, 3 March 2024, Grandmother, Mother, my younger sister (Klu mo mtsho, b. 2006), and I performed the ritual. Mother prepared two scoops of water - one with milk and one without. Water-only was poured over the yaks before tying the *srung rtags* to the yaks' manes. Next, butter was smeared on the horns, forehead, and muzzle. Finally, water with milk was poured over the yaks. If the yaks shook, it indicated that the guardian deities were pleased.

On Monday, 5 March 2024, Mother reported numerous parasites on the yaks' hair, especially on the calves. She had treated the parasites several times in the past month, but they persisted. She then purchased a parasite poison from Mgo mang (Guomaying) Town. It was hard to apply to the yak's skin because of its strong smell, making the yak flee. Consequently, she mixed ash with the poison, reducing the odor. When Mother was younger, her grandmother used ash or rapeseed oil to treat yak parasites, which proved effective. Mother also used rapeseed oil to treat yak parasites, but it was only temporarily effective. I didn't help her much because I was recording, but I gave them oil while they were treating the yaks for parasites.

TIBETAN TERMS

a myes dam chen mgar ba nag po ཨ་མྱེས་དམ་ཅན་མག་བ་ནག་པོ།

a myes glang chen ཨ་མྱེས་གླང་ཅེན།

a myes rma chen ཨ་མྱེས་རྩ་ཅེན།

bla ma ལྷ་མ།

dkar mo rgyal དཀར་མོ་རྒྱལ།

dpa' ldan lha mo དཔལ་འདུན་ལྷ་མོ།

gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།

mang zdong མང་རྫོང།

mgo mang མགོ་མང།

mstho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

mstho snon མཚོ་སྐོན།

rgaya kho ལྷོ་ལོ།

sha rgya ཤ་རྒྱ།

sman chu'i a ma lab sgron ma སྐན་ཚུའི་ཨ་མ་ལ་བ་ལྷོན་མ།

srung rtags སྤང་རྟགས།

yul lha ཡུལ་ལྷ།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南

Guomaying 过马营

Hainan 海南

Qinghai 青海

TAYINSUUNI DANGMANI HGAIJA DA QINSANGNI NANTARI¹

Limusishiden (Li Dechun 李得春), Joint Surgery Department,
Qinghai University Affiliated Hospital

43 minutes

<https://archive.org/details/tayinsuuni-dangmani-hgaija-da-qinsangni-nantari>

Limusishiden's Mongghul language audio recording is of an article written in the Mongghul language: Limusishiden. 2023. Tayinsuuni Dangmani Hgaija da qinsangniini Nantari. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 63:201-218.

<https://archive.org/details/tayinsuuni-dangmani-hgaija-da-qinsangniini-nantari/page/218/mode/2up>

GAQANNIINI DOGLA

Tayinsuu (1968 fandi turaja), Mongghul, ghuran bulaini aamana. Ne Dunda Lusni, Kugua Noori Snni, Huzhuu Mongghul Njeena Dolagu Xanni Jughuari Ayilidigu yiringa. Turaji bosa huhuunga; jina ayilini mula surighualira tawun fan pujiu muxija; mulani sghuudi ghadadi kashida aasi dilaja. Zhinyahua (1950 fandi turaja), Tayinsuuni aamana, gan Tayinsuudi ne hgaija suugahgina sanglidi ghuja. Ne pujiura Tayinsuuni kuduguniini guleji, hgaija suuganiini,arang Tayinsuuni aamani aagu lama lasani jiuriwa. Ne 2020 fanni Ghoori Sarani 29di bu Tayinsuuni kuduni xji ganla tangxalaji, ne pujiuni jiuri burawa.

¹ Limusishiden (Li Dechun 李得春). 2025. Tayinsuuni Dangmani Hgaija da Qinsngni Nantari. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:261.

KHRO GRYAL, TIBETAN TRADITIONAL SINGER

Gser mo mtsho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措)¹

12 minutes 37 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11103263>

I recorded Khro rgyal (b. 1951), my neighbor, from Sha rgya (Shajia) Community, Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho Lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China on Saturday, 30 March 2024, at my home in Sha rgya (Shajia) Community. He sings traditional Tibetan songs exceptionally well. He is the father of fifteen children.

Two of his children passed away in a car accident. Khro rgyal confided that losing his children had diminished his interest in singing. He added that most of the lyrics he once knew had faded from his memory. However, he had an excellent memory in his youth and could remember songs after hearing them only once at weddings.

Khro rgyal is also a skilled herder. His family owns nearly 500 sheep. He counted sheep almost every night, and if a few were missing, he knew the missing ones. He knows every animal in the community and which animals belong to which family, so community members often consult him when they lose livestock.

Khro rgyal remains an active herder and often visits my home, which is a twenty-minute walk from his home, after tending his sheep. My family always welcomes him and prepares food for him.

¹ Gser mo mtsho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措). 2025. Khro rgyal, Tibetan Traditional Singer. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:262-263.

TIBETAN TERMS

khro rgyal ཁོ་རྒྱལ།

mang rzung མང་རྩེང།

mgo mang མགོ་མང།

mtso lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

mtso sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།

sha rgya ཤ་རྒྱ།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南

Guomaying 过马营

Hainan 海南

Qinghai 青海

Shajia 沙加

A TIBETAN DOCTOR COLLECTS MEDICINAL HERBS IN MTSHO LHO, A MDO¹

Bkra shis rgya mtsho བཀྲ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ། (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措)

Photographer, writer, editor: Bkra shis rgya mtsho བཀྲ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

Filmed with an iPhone 12 Pro Max)

Date: Monday, 24 July 2023

20 minutes 23 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10677031>

This film features a Tibetan local doctor (Lha snang gyal, bl 1970) collecting herbs at 34 °48'6" latitude, 100°40'12" longitude, 4,493 MASL on Ba wo Mountain, Rmog dkar (Muhe) Village, Zhol ma (Xiuma) Town, 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

PART ONE: INTRODUCTION

Lha snang gyal was born in Brigade Number Three, Klu lung (Lilun) Village, Thang mgo (Tanggu) Town, 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. After completing local primary school, he spent a couple of years at home assisting his parents in herding livestock.

At eighteen, he began studying *Tibetan Four Medical Tantras* under the guidance of his paternal uncle, Thub bstan dam chos 'od zer (1966-2019), a local scholar-monk. Subsequently, he gained clinical experience for three years at a

¹ Bkra shis rgya mtsho བཀྲ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ། (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措). 2025. A Tibetan Doctor Collects Medicinal Herbs in Mtsho lho, A mdo. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65: 264-276.

local County Tibetan hospital (Tongde Xian Zang Yiyuan), working alongside Dr. Mkhar 'bum gyal, specializing in ear-related cases.

For an additional two years, he served at the Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Provincial Tibetan Hospital (Qinghai Sheng Zang Yiyuan), collaborating with his paternal uncle, Blo 'ba' (b. 1948), in the Internal Medicine, Surgery, and Infectious Diseases departments.

In 2005, with Blo 'ba', he established a branch of the Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Provincial Tibetan Hospital in 'Ba' thang, his home area, where he worked for three years. Concurrently, he furthered his education, graduating from Chab cha Technical School's Medical Department (Hainan Zhou Zhiye Jishu Xuexiao) in 2009 and Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Provincial Medical University (Qinghai Daxue Yixueyuan) in 2011.

Following academic achievements, he worked for two years at Sde dge zhe chen sman khang kun phan bde skyid gling, also known as Sde dge zhe chen Tibetan Medicine Clinic (Dege Xieqing Lizhong Fule Yiyuan), located in Zhe chen (Xieqing) Monastery, Rdzogs chen (Zuoqin) Township, Sde dge (Dege) County, Dkar mdzes (Ganzi) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Si khron (Sichuan) Province.

In 2014, Lha snang gyal successfully passed an examination and obtained the National Doctor Qualification Certificate. In 2015, he acquired a National Medical Practice Certificate. In 2016, he returned to 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) and established a private clinic - 'Sapphire Tibetan Clinic' (Laroujia Zangyi Zhensuo) - in the local County Town. Afterward, he has been committed to providing quality healthcare services for the community.

COLLECTING HERBS ON THE MOUNTAIN

This morning, we prepared bread and beverages for lunch. I (b. 1983) joined my brother, Lha snang rgyal; sister-in-law, Nyi ma lha mo (b.1996); and nephew Bsod nams bkra shis (b. 2014). We

traveled 115 kilometers to collect *cochalaria scapiflora*. Unfortunately, we couldn't find this particular herb. Instead, we gathered around twenty kilograms of *lagotis crassifolia* Prain in two plastic bags with two small hoes.

We had come to this area a year earlier and collected herbs near Ra rgya Town. The collection took place on the mountain from 1:10 p.m. to 6:00 p.m., during which we also had lunch.

Upon returning to the foot of the mountain, we washed all the herbs in a stream.

HERB COLLECTION GUIDELINES

SELECTING THE DATE

Every year, the first day of herb collection should be chosen based on the Tibetan lunisolar calendar, specifically opting for a day with the "Water-Water combination." This day is auspicious, as the double encounter of water brings together nectar, enhancing life's force.

SELECTIVE HARVESTING

While collecting herbs, it is essential not to harvest all of certain plants that you locate. You should leave some behind and express a prayer for preserving the plant species. This practice aligns with the principle of ensuring sustainability and addressing the needs of patients suffering from various diseases.

SPIRITUAL PREPARATION

Before venturing into the field, it is best to invoke the blessings of the Medicine Buddhas by reciting the Medicine Prayer scripture. Face the east and prostrate three times to the east, emphasizing the healing potency of the herbs to address all ailments. Exercise caution in language, avoiding any expressions

that might arouse suspicion, particularly refraining from labeling the herbs poisonous plants.

HYGIENIC PRACTICES

After collecting herbs, wash them in local water before bringing them home. This ensures cleanliness and removes impurities adhering to the plants during collection.

EXPERIENCES IN COLLECTING MATERIALS

Over the decades of my brother's experience collecting plants, he has observed a decline in the overall plant population, with some species on the brink of extinction in certain areas. The demand of the social market encourages the use of local medicine due to the increasing influx of outsiders engaging in business, impacting the requirements of local doctors and the overall healthcare landscape.

Second, the entire ecosystem is degraded due to land excavation and water and air contamination. Additionally, there have been instances of encountering danger while collecting herbs on mountains and digging soil and stones for medicinal purposes. For instance, in 2017, I (writer) assisted my brother in collecting calcite on a cliff. I narrowly avoided a fall into melting snow on slippery foothills. Another time, while accompanied by two nephews on a foggy summer day in the mountains, we reached the top of the mountain, and I lost sight of my nephews until the fog dissipated later in the evening.

PART TWO

This section explores how locals employ their imagery of herbs, associating them with various animals and objects, to describe and identify herbs. I translated these descriptions into English from the local terms. Additionally, photographs depict the process of collecting medicinal materials and highlight instances of treating patients.

LOCALLY RECOGNIZED HERBS

Gentiana urnula H. Smith: Resembles the nine layers of a wheel.

Swertia chirayita Buch. -han: Resembles a raven carrying an arrow.

Black *Pulicaria insignis* Drumm: Similar to a metal smoking pipe.

Lagotis yunnanensis W. Smith: Resembles the matted hair of a dog's tail.

Chrysosplenium carnosum Hook: Resembling a horse hoof.

Thlaspi arvense L: Resembles a small Bon tradition drum.

Aster himalaicus Clarke: Resembles a sword-wheel.

Codonopsis nervosa Nannf: Like a small metal bell.

Dracocephalum tanguticum Maxim: Like a hinny's mane.

Lagotis brachystachya Maxim: Similar to a calf tether line in a prosperous household.

Hypecoum leptocarpum Hook: Similar to a rich father's daughter.

Saxifraga melanocentra: Like broken black barley.

Lancea tibetica Hook.F.et Hsuan: Resembles a raven's eye.

Meconopsis horridula Hook: Resembles a shameful bride.

Przewalskia tangutica Maxim.: Like an old man's scrotum.

Rhodiola wallichiana: Resembles a horse's lung.

Saussurea medusa Maxim: Similar to a doe's throat.

Saxifraga umbelluata Hook: Resembles setting a fire on grassland.

Pedicularis tubiformis Tsoong: Resembles a vulture looking backward.

Capsella bursa-pastoris Medic: Like a lamb's shoulder blade.

Thamnolia vermicularia: Resembles a deer's white antler.

Lamiophlomis rotata (Benth.) Kudo: Resembles the skin of an old man's chest.

Aconitum naviculare Stapf: Similar to a vulture's curved beak.

Arenaria kansuensis Maxim: Resembles the grass in a yak's stomach turned inside out.

Polygonum macrophyllum D. Don: Resembles an unsheared male sheep.

Pulicaria insignis Drumm: Similar to a tassel on a monk's horse's chest.

Paeonia tenuifolia var. *lutea* Marq: Resembles conch earrings.

Ligularia virgaurea: Resembles donkey ears.

Incarvillea compacta Maxim: Resembles a wolf's nipple.

Cordyceps: Resembles a rhinoceros's horn.

ལྷ་བདུད་རྩོམ་ལྷགས་ཀྱི་འཕྲུལ་ལྟར་འདྲ།
 གཞུ་རྒྱུང་ནི་འཁོར་ལོ་དབྱེ་བཞེགས་འདྲ།
 གཡའ་ཀྱི་ཚྭ་ལོ་རྩ་ཚོད་མིག་པ་འདྲ།
 ལྷ་སྒང་(མོན་ལུ་)དཀར་པོ་ག་གཟན་བལ་ལུར་འདྲ།
 ཉིག་ཏུ་ནག་པོ་ཕོ་རོག་མདའ་ལུར་འདྲ།
 ཐང་ཁྲོམ་དཀར་པོ་མི་རྒྱན་རྒྱུག་པ་འདྲ།
 ཇི་ཡང་གི་ནི་རྩེ་ལྷ་རྒྱུང་རྩོག་མ་འདྲ།
 བ་ཡག་པ་ནི་ཕོ་རོག་མིག་རྩོག་འདྲ།
 བྱ་ཚོད་ལུག་པ་ལྷ་མོའི་ཨོལ་ཚོག་འདྲ།
 བར་བ་ཏུ་ནི་ཕ་ལྷགས་བྱ་མོ་འདྲ།
 ཇིག་བ་ནི་བོན་པོའི་རྩ་རྒྱུང་འདྲ།
 བོང་བ་དཀར་པོ་ཚོད་ཀྱི་ཡ་མཚུ་འདྲ།
 མིང་ཅན་ནག་པོ་ལྷགས་ནག་དུང་ཚོག་(ར་ཙོ་)འདྲ།
 མིང་ཅན་མེར་པོ་སྤྲོ་མའི་རྫོང་དྲིམ་འདྲ།
 འབྲུ་ཏུ་མ་འཛོན་ལྷགས་པོའི་བེུ་རྩང་འདྲ།
 འོད་ལྗན་དཀར་པོ་ནས་ནག་ཚོག་ཚོ་འདྲ།
 རྒྱལ་བའི་རྒྱུན་ནི་རལ་མའི་འཁོར་ལོ་འདྲ།
 རྩ་ལྷགས་པ་ནི་མི་རྒྱན་བྲང་བགས་འདྲ།
 རྩ་ད་བྱིད་བམེ་བའི་ར་ཙོ་འདྲ།
 རི་ཤོ་པ་(ཁོ་ཤོག)ནི་ཤོང་བའི་རྩ་མཚོག་འདྲ།
 ལི་ག་དུར་རྩ་སྤོ་བཅོས་མ་འདྲ།
 ལུག་ཕ་མེར་པོ་བྱ་ཚོད་ལྱིར་བཞུས་འདྲ།
 ལྷང་ཚན་དཀར་པོ་ཤ་བོའི་དུང་ར་འདྲ།
 ལྷོ་ལོ་དཀར་པོ་དུང་མའི་རྩ་རྩོག་འདྲ།
 ལུམ་ཅུ་ཉིག་ནི་ལྷང་ལ་མེ་ཤོར་འདྲ།
 སོག་ཀ་པ་ནི་ལུག་རྒྱུང་མོག་པ་འདྲ།
 རྩོང་ལེན་ཚྭ་ལོ་ཁྱི་ཡི་རྩ་འབྲིང་འདྲ།

ཨ་གྲོང་དཀར་པོ་གཡག་ཆེན་ལྷོ་(ལྷོ་ཚོགས་)འདྲ།
ཨ་བྱག་ཚོ་ཚོན་བག་མ་ཚུལ་འདུག་(ཚུལ་རིམ་)འདྲ།
ལྷག་ཚོས་ལྷོ་དམར་ལྷུང་གི་བེ་རྩ་མ་འདྲ།

PART THREE: LHA SNANG GYAL'S CLINIC

Lha snang gyal has treated thousands of patients over eight years. His clinic currently houses around seventy types of Tibetan medicine, with approximately forty acquired from Lha sa, Sde dge, Mdzod dge, and other medical factories and hospitals, and he has created around thirty. This collection includes formulations such as Six Pacification, Eight *Gentiana chretta*, Twelve Calcite by Phagmotrupa, twenty-five mulberry formulations, twenty-five bamboo manna, white pills, and more.

The process of collecting herbal materials involves leaves, flowers, seeds, and roots. In summer, he focuses on collecting various plants, including three types of *mecopsis punicea*, blue *meconopsis horridual* Hook, *oxygraphis glacialis*, *aster souliei* Franch, dragonhead, three types of sheep horns, two types of *gentians*, *gentaina decumbens*, *soroseris hookeriana*, snow lotus, *lagotis crassifolia*, and many others. Additionally, herbs with roots, such as *orchis latifolia*, *rheum palmatum*, fritillary bulbs, *Lancea tibetica* Hook, and *miliaris himalaica*, are harvested in autumn and winter.

His clinic also has hundreds of soil and stone medicinal materials, including two types of white stones, snow droplets, calcite, bamboo manna, and others. The inventory extends to Tibetan medicinal materials such as mineral waters, soils, stones, herbs, animals, and animal dung.

A saying suggests that an informed mixing of substances can turn anything into medicine. Moreover, lying on the grassland, a person's body surrounded by grass can purportedly cure a range of illnesses.

TIBETAN TERMS

- baiDUr+ya bod sman khang འི་རྒྱུ་བོད་སྐྱེན་ཁང་།
- bkra shis rgya mtsho བག་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
- blo 'ba' ལྷོ་འབའ།
- bsod nams bkra shis བསོད་ནམས་བག་ཤིས།
- dga' rab དགའ་རབ།
- dkar mdzes དཀར་མཛེས།
- lha snang rgyal ལྷ་སྐང་རྒྱལ།
- mkhar 'bum rgyal མཁར་འབུམ་རྒྱལ།
- nyi ma lha mo ཉི་མ་ལྷ་མོ།
- ra rgya ར་རྒྱ།
- rdzogs chen རྫོགས་ཚེན།
- rgyal bo རྒྱལ་བོ།
- sde dge zhe chen sman khang kun phan bde skyid gling
ཕྱེ་དགེ་ཞེ་ཚེན་སྐྱེན་ཁང་ཀུན་པས་བདེ་སྦྱིད་གླིང་།
- sde dge ཕྱེ་དགེ།
- si khron སི་ཁྲོན།
- thub bstan dam chos 'od zer ཐུབ་བསྟན་དམ་ཚུལ་འདྲ་ཟེེ།

CHINESE TERMS

- Dege 德格
- Dege Xieqing Lizhong Fule Yiyuan 德格协庆利众福乐医院
- Ganzi 甘孜
- Hainan Zhou Zhiye Jishu Xuexiao 海南州职业技术学校
- Hainan 海南
- Laroujia Zangyi Zhensuo 拉肉加藏医诊所
- Lilun 力伦
- Muhe 木合
- Qinghai 青海
- Qinghai Daxue Yixueyuan 青海大学医学院
- Qinghai Sheng Zang Yiyuan 青海省藏医院
- Sichuan 四川
- Tanggu 唐谷
- Tongde Xian Zang Yiyuan 同德县藏医院

Tongde 同德

Xieqing 协庆

Xiuma 秀麻

Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措

Zuoqin 佐钦

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DIALOGUE

Oh, A+yon chos sgron.

Sound of a car.

Tragic, look at this, such a bad road, not the road to take. Drive slowly.

It's sure to be a waste.

We probably arrived at that mountain last year.

There aren't many car tracks here.

Sheep bleating.

The sound of chewing gum.

Sheep bleating.

They are gathering here.

Go up and give it to Mother.

Uncle, look down, it's so beautiful.

The sound of footsteps. Have you had lunch? It looks like there's caterpillar fungus around. Quickly eat and go.

Bsod b+ha, Da ran (sound), hum.

Are there 300 sheep? More than 300.

When were we coming here? At 9 a.m.? No, we came here last year, maybe at the same time.

Did we arrive earlier last year?

Are they arriving at the summer pasture at that time? Probably.

Last year was earlier than this year. Did you come here before last year?

Bsod b+ha came here last time, didn't he? I don't remember. Mthu b+ha was sick and we went to collect medicine.

I don't remember.

When we returned, we brought 5 kilograms of milk.

Are you happy to go and collect medicine? Happy but cold. It's okay.

Have you collected herbs before? Tell me all the places you went to.

All the bread is finished. Is it enough?

I don't know, ask Lha Lha.

The sound of small birds.

Oh, why did you come here? I came to collect herbs. Is it hard work? A little bit.

Uncle came here, and the butterflies were fluttering.

The sound of butterfly wings.

What's that? It's wild garlic.

This is wonderful. Pop.

What's that? Came here. I don't know exactly.

Father, what's the name of the flower I'm collecting?

It is *Aster himalaicus* Clarke.

Oh, it's called *Aster himalaicus* Clarke.

Mother said to help her. Lha lha said to help him.

In fact, who am I to help?

Lha lha, where should this be placed? Give it to Mother Nyi ma.

Bsod nams bkra shis, collect all, don't leave any behind.

Oh, Bsod nams bkra shis, there it is.

Now, the bag is really full.

Can you carry it back home? I can't.

Sound of walking.

Arenaria kansuensis Maxim resembles the sound of grass in a yak's stomach turning inside out.

Giggle. Resembles the sound of grass in a yak's stomach turning inside.

This is *Saxifraga melanocentra*, resembling broken black barley.
What is this grass? This is *Saussurea areanaria* Maxim.

Polygonum macrophyllum D. Don: Resembles unshered wool
on a male sheep.

Is this it? Yes, it is.

This is also called *Polygonum sinomontanum* Sam. It's a lung
medicinal herb. This is called *Aster himalaicus* Clarke,
Aster flaccidus Bunge, and also lotus.

Here lies a dead insect. Giggle.

Yes, put it in your mouth to check its taste. It's delicious.

Taraxacum tibetanum Hand heals wounds and fevers.

Do you know this? *Aconitum naviculare* Stapf heals epidemic
poison and old fever. Let's go.

Eat it. Giggle, do you like it? Hum.

The sound of a stream.

Children's voices.

ལ་བད།
 འ་ལོ། ལྷོན་ཚོས་སྒྲོན།
 རྒྱངས་འཁོར་སྒོ་རྒྱབ་པའི་སྤྱ།
 རེ། ད་འདི་རེད་ཡ། ལམ་ཚོག་འོ། དེ་འགྲོ་ས་ཞིག་མ་རེད། དལ་མོ་གྱིས།
 ད་ལན་ཆགས་ཁོ་ཐག་གོ་རེད།
 ར་ཉིང་འུ་ཚོ་བྱད་སའི་ལ་གན་ཡིན་ལ་རེད།
 འདི་ན་རྒྱངས་འཁོར་སོང་ཤལ་མང་པོ་མི་འདུག
 ལྷག་གི་འབའ་སྤྱ།
 ཐང་རྒྱ་ལྷད་པའི་སྤྱ།
 ཁོ་ཚོས་འདི་ན་འབྲུ་གི་འདུག
 ཡར་ལ་སོང་། ཨ་མ་བྱིན།
 ཨ་མ་ཁྱོས་མར་ལ་སྒོས་དང་ད་ཡག་གི་ཡ།
 གོ་མ་སྤྱ། ལྷོད་ཚོས་དྲོས་ཇ་འཐུང་ཀོ་ནས། ལྷན་རྒྱ་ཡོང་ཡོད་འདོད་ས་ཞིག་རེད།
 དེ་མ་ཟ་དང་ནས་འགྲོ།
 བསོད་རྒྱ་སྤྱི་བྱན་ཅན་པོ་དེ། འུན།
 ལྷག་ཤལ་ཡག་པ་བྱས་ཡོད་ཀེ་ད། ཤལ་ཡིས་མི་ཚད་ཀེ།
 འུ་ཚོ་ནམ་ཡོང་ནི་ཡིན་ད། དུས་ཚིད་དགའི་སྤོང་ཡོང་ནི་རེད།
 མ་རེད་ན་ཉིང་འུ་ཚོ་ཡོང་དུས། ཐལ་ཆེར་ད་ཚོད་ཅིག་ཡིན་རྒྱུ་རེད།
 ར་ཉིང་དོ་རྒྱགས་ཀེ་ཐ་ཡིན་ནི་རེད། འདི་ཚོ་དབྱར་སའི་ནང་ལ་བབས་མེད་ཀ་ཡིན། བབས་ཡོད་ན་ཡང་ཐང་གི་
 བབ་འདུག ལུ་ཡར་ལ་ན་ཡོད་འོ། དེའི་སྒྲན་ལ་འདིར་འབྲུ་གི་ཡོང་ཨ་སྤོང་། མ་སྤོང་།

བསོད་སྒྲུ་ཡང་དེ་དུས་ཡོང་ང་། ཞེ་ཡོང་ད། ཡིད་ལ་མི་ཡོང་གི།
 མཐུ་སྒྲ་ཅིག་ན་ནས་ཉལ་བཟང་ནས་འུ་ཚོ་འཐུ་གི་སོང་ནི་མི་དྲན་གི། ཁི་ཡོང་གི།
 འོ་མ་རྒྱ་མ་བརྒྱ་ཐུམ་པ་ཁྲུང་ནས་ཕྱིར་ལ་སོང་ནོ།
 ཐུན་འཐུ་གི་སོང་ན་ཞེ་བསོ་གི་བསོད་ལྷ། བསོད་གི་ར་གྲང་གི། བྲང་ན་དྲག་ནི་རེད། དེ་མིན་ཁྱོད་ཐུན་འཐུ་གི་གང་ལ་སོང་ར། སོང་ས་
 ཚང་མ་ཤོད།
 ཞོ་རེ་ཉུང་འདུག་ཚར་སོང་ནི་རེད་ནས།
 དེ་ཤེས་ནི་མ་རེད། ལྷ་ལྷ་འདྲི་དགོས་ནི་རེད།
 རྩེའུ་ཡི་སྐད་སྒྲ།
 འ་རོ་ཁྱོད་ཅི་ཁྱོད་དུ་ཡོང་བ་ཡིན། ཐུན་འཐུ་གི་ཐུན་འཐུ་རྒྱ་འདི་ཞེ་དཀའ་ལྷོ་རྒྱ་ཚམ་དཀའ་ལྷོ།
 ཨ་མ་མེ་མ་ལེ་བ། རྩེ་མ་ལེ་བ་ཀྱི་གཤོག་སྒྲ།
 དེ་ཅི་རེད། རྩེ་སྒྲོག།
 འདི་ད་འཇིགས་གི་ཡ།
 ཚིག་ཤོད།
 ཀའ་རེ་དེ་ཅི་ཞིག་རེད། མི་ཤེས་གི།
 ཨ་པ་ངས་འཐུ་གོ་ནི་མེ་རྟོག་གན་གི་ཕྱིར་ལ་ཅི་ཞིག་ཡིན་ད།
 ཐུན་རིས་གཟིགས་རྟོག་ཏུ་ཟེར་ནི་རེད།
 ཨ། མི་རྟོག་རྟོག་ཏུ་ཟེར་ནི་རེད།
 མི་རྟོག་རྟོག་ཏུ་ཟེར་གི། ཀའ་ལོངས་དང་།
 དེ་ཅི་རེད། ལྷ་ལྷས་ང་ལེན་རྟོགས་ཏུས་ཟེར། ཨ་མ་ཉི་མས་ཡང་ང་ལེན་རྟོགས་ཏུས་ཟེར།
 དོན་ངོ་མ་ལུང་ལེན་རྟོགས་ཏུ་དགོས་ནི་རེད།
 ལྷ་ལྷ་འདི་གང་ལ་འཇོག་སྒྲ། ཨ་མ་ཉི་མ་ཁྱོད་ཚོངས།
 བསོད་ནམས་བཀའ་ཤིས་ལེར་བཟིག་ར་མ་རྒྱར་ནས་འཐུས།
 བསོད་ནམས་བཀའ་ཤིས་དེ་རེད། འ་རོ།
 ད་ངེས་ངེ་གང་ཐལ་གོ།
 དེ་ཁྱོས་ཁྲུང་ནས་འགྲོ་དགོས་ན་བ་ས་ཞེ་ཡོང་གི། ངས་བ་རྒྱ་མ་རེད་གོ།
 ཞོ་མ་སྒྲ།
 ཨ་ཀྲོང་དཀའ་ར་པོ་གཡག་གན་སྒྲོ་རྟོགས་འདྲ། ཏུ་ཏུ་གཡམ་གན་སྒྲོ་རྟོགས་འདྲ།
 འོད་ཐུན་དཀའ་ར་པོ་ནས་རྟོག་ཆོ་འདྲ་འདི་རེད།
 ལྷ་དེ་ཅི་རེད། ལྷ་མ་ཁྲིས་བ་མོ་ལ།
 མོན་ཏུ་དཀའ་ར་པོ་གཡམ་བལ་ཁྲུང་འདྲ་ཟེར་ནི་རེད།
 འདི་ཡིན་ནི་ཞེ་རེད། ཡིན་ནི་རེད།
 འདི་ལེ་མིང་ལ་སྐྱ་སྐང་ཡང་ཟེར། ཐུན་ཐུན་ཞིག་ཡིན་ནི་རེད།
 འདི་ལ་རྒྱལ་བའི་ཐུན་ཟེར་ནི་རེད། རྟོག་ཏུ་ཡང་ཟེར་ནི་རེད། ལྷ་རྒྱལ་ཡང་ཟེར།
 བང་ན་འཐུ་ཞིག་ཤི་འདུག་དགོང་སྒྲ།
 འོ་ལེ། དེ་ལྷར་འར་བཞག་ནས་རོ་ཅི་ཡིན་བརྟོག་དགོས།
 འདི་ཞིམ་གི་ཡ།

ལུང་མོང་མ་ཡི་ཚ་བ་སེལ་བར་བྱེད་ཟེར། །
ཨ་ཤེས་ཀྱི་བོང་ང་དཀར་པོས་རིམས་དུག་རྩིང་ཚད་སེལ། །
ད་འགྲོ།
འདི་ཚོ། ཉ་ཉ། ལྷོད་ཟ་རྒྱུར་དགའ་ཀ
ཨ་དགའ། ལུན།
ཚུ་ཕན་གྱི་བུའུར་རྒྱ།
ལྷིས་པའི་རྐང་རྒྱ།

OFFERING ROAST BARLEY FLOUR TO ANTS ON THE MOUNTAIN¹

Bkra shis rgya mtsho བཀྲ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ། (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措)

3 minutes 51 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10533954>

Wednesday, 16 August 2023 - 10:25 a.m. to 1:14 p.m.

Filmed with an iPhone 12 Pro Max.

This film highlights a local ritual of offering roast barley flour to ants on the mountain during an annual summer festival in the Sman lung Valley, Shar tshang Village, Rka 'ba' sum mdo Town, 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

My nephew (Bsod nams bkra shis, b. 2014) and I (Bkra shis rgya mtsho, b. 1983) participated in this festival in Shar tshang Village. On 15 August 2023 my friend (Rgyal po b. 1973) informed me they were ready. The next day, on August 16 in the early morning, I drove my brother's Forth car to Shar tshang Village around nine a.m. My friend and his grandson (Rdo rje don 'grub, b. 2017) joined us when we reached his home. We spent two hours pouring *rtsam pa* in a nest of ants on the mountain and collecting sea buckthorn. When we returned to the foot of the mountain, the village religious leader, A lag ('Jigs med rgya mtsho, b. 1963), and other participants, who had been waiting, seized the opportunity when the rain stopped to prepare and offer roast barley flour incense, accompanied by chanting rituals and prayers.

¹ Bkra shis rgya mtsho བཀྲ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ། (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措). 2025. Offering Roast Barley Flour to Ants on the Mountain. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:277-285.

According to Buddhist practitioners, generosity serves two purposes. First, it is directed towards individuals who have embraced bodhicitta. Secondly, according to Buddhist theory, it includes sentient beings in lower realms, such as ants, who endure suffering in the form of an animal body and mental suffering as hungry ghosts. Generous offerings in this context yield significant merit. The ritual holds profound motivation in allowing ants to connect with the Dharma and plant the seeds of enlightenment for their future lives. Additionally, practitioners encompass three types of generosity in this ritual: the generosity of life, the generosity of subsistence, and the generosity of the Dharma.

The ritual aims to facilitate healing and wealth accumulation for individuals with guidance from local diviners. For example, some diviners suggested that their followers do this to overcome misfortune and avoid obstacles in their future lives. Barley flour is finely ground to initiate the ritual, ensuring its purity without animal flesh. The resulting powder should be treated with reverence, like a peaceful Buddha relic pill. This sacred powder, which encompasses the five dharmas of Buddhahood without meditation, seeing, hearing, thinking, touching, and tasting to attain enlightenment and sow the seeds of enlightenment, should not be combined with a wrathful Buddha's pill.

When necessary conditions are met, a monk will lead participants in specific ritual chants and use a sacred conch to summon ants from their nests.

CONTEXT

This ritual originated in a thousand-year-old tradition documented in Buddhist scriptures, particularly in the renowned work *The Precious Garland* by the Mahayana Buddhist master Nagarjuna (150-250 CED). While not specifically centered on ants, the text mentions providing food to insects and highlights associated merits. From a Buddhist

perspective, offering sustenance to ants is considered exceptionally meritorious because it extends compassion to hungry ghosts who experience great suffering from thirst and hunger. In Buddhist philosophy, the hierarchy of merit is established, with acts of generosity towards ants more extraordinary than similar acts to hungry people, ordinary individuals, monks, or even ant colonies. Following this ancient tradition, the ritual was practiced many years ago by a religious figure who collaborated with local community members in my home community.

THE CONTEMPORARY SITUATION AND MY EXPERIENCES

Throughout history, various scriptures have emphasized the practice of offering roast barley flour to ants. Such texts suggest mixing roast barley powder with a small amount of yak butter, imbuing it with religious sanctity, and sprinkling it on the periphery of an ant's nest. A crucial condition is ensuring there is no rain after scattering the roast barley flour in the ant nest, as rain could prove fatal to the ants.

More recently, some monks mix holy substances with water and add them to watermelon for the ants, believing that these substances can alleviate the suffering of hunger and thirst. However, most locals, including me, continue to adhere to the traditional practice of offering roast barley flour to ants.

My mother (Gangs mtsho skyid, 1950-2018) shared stories of a local holy monk, O'u rgya dge zhe'u rin po che (Thub bstan 'jam dbyangs dge legs dpal bzang, 1917-1959), who, each summer before the Culture Revolution (1966-1976), performed this ritual in the local community. In the autumn of 2018, my friend 'Jam dbyangs mkhyen rab (b. 1982, a monk) and my older brother (Lha snang rgyal, b. 1979) dedicated a day to offering *rtsam pa* to ants on the mountain on my friend's family winter pasture.

This marks my second time to participate in this ritual.

SUNDAY, 20 AUGUST 2023 - 12:31 a.m.-3:12 p.m.

I set off to offer roast barley flour to ants on the mountain with my friends, 'Jam dbyangs mkhyen rab (b. 1982), 'Jigs med shes rab (b. 1983), and Gro'u pe (b. 1952).

After planning a few days earlier, we selected a date with clear weather, ensuring no rain. Each of us contributed fifty RMB, to purchase ten kilograms of roast barley flour in plastic bags. Additionally, we bought drinks, watermelons, a bottle of yogurt, and fruit from a County Town shop for our lunch and fuel for the car. The day before our journey, I assisted Zhu bae in crushing religious substances with a mortar and pestle, combining them with sugar, and mixing it all with the roast barley flour.

Our destination was one hundred kilometers away in Brag ser Valley, Thar shul Village, Thar shul Town, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China, where we aimed to find numerous ant nests.

We arrived near She'u lung sman zhing Valley, offered incense and roast barley flour, and had lunch there.

TIBETAN TERMS

- 'ba' rdzong འབའ་རྫོང་།
- 'jam dbyangs mkhyen rab འཇམ་དབྱངས་མཁྱེན་རབ།
- 'jigs med shes rab འཇིགས་མེད་ཤེས་རབ།
- a lag 'jigs med rgya mtsho ཨ་ལག་འཇིགས་མེད་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
- bkra shis rgya mtsho བག་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
- brag ser བྲག་སེར།
- bsod nams bkra shis བསོད་ནམས་བག་ཤིས།
- gangs mtsho skyid གངས་མཚོ་སྐྱེད།
- gro'u pe གྲོ་ལེ།
- lha snang rgyal ལྷ་སྣང་རྒྱལ།
- mang rdzong མང་རྫོང་།
- mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
- mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྐོན།

o'u rgya dge zhe'u rin po che ཨོལ་རྒྱ་དགེ་ཞེ་འུ་རིན་པོ་ཆེ།

rdo rje don 'grub རྡོ་རྗེ་དོན་འགྲུབ།

rgyal po རྒྱལ་པོ།

rka 'ba' sum mdo ཀ་འབའ་སུམ་མདོ།

rtsam pa རྩམ་པ།

shar tshang ཤར་ཚང།

she'u lung sman zhing ཤེ་འུ་ལུང་སྐྱམ་ཟིང།

sman lung སྐྱམ་ལུང།

thar shul ཐར་ཤུ།

thub bstan 'jam dbyangs dge legs dpal bzang

ཐུབ་བསྐྱེན་འཇམ་དབྱངས་དགེ་ལེགས་དཔལ་བཟང།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南

Qinghai 青海

Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措

Hainan 海南

Tongde 同德

SCRIPT

Children while walking.

We are here to climb.

A conch.

The *rtsam pa* is already poured here.

Is there poured *rtsam pa*?

Reciting the mantras of the unshakable Buddha and the
compassionate Buddha.

Approaching autumn, the ants are born with wings.

Reciting " *oM ma Ni pad+me hU~M.*"

Go, brother.

Sea buckthorn has various qualities.

The ant is good.

Reciting the mantras of the unshakable Buddha and the
compassionate Buddha.

After growing up, pour his way.

Yes.

Do you understand? Yes.

We shouted, and many ants came.

Poured around the edge of the ant nest.

Don't pour too much.

Don't scatter on the top of the nest; scatter here.

How many ants are here?

A conch.

One *bla ma* said, "Watermelon is good." But our *bla ma* said,

"*Rtsam pa* is good." Anyway, people said, their own *bla ma* is a flower, and their *bla ma* is grass.

Children imitate the conch sound.

How many ant nests did we scatter around?

We should count them.

Wow, I make the conch sound.

There is a huge black bee.

Oh.

Our community went to offer incense on the black rocky mountain.

Oh, if someone needs more *rtsam pa*, come and I will give you.

What would you like?

Do you drink Pepsi?

A conch.

Pour *rtsam pa* this way.

Chanting the compassionate Buddha's mantra.

Are you here to feed the ants today?

Yes.

How many nests did you offer to?

Twenty or thirty.

To collect sea buckthorn.

Sea buckthorn covered everywhere.

Cannot root up the sea buckthorn.

Are there a lot of people?

About how many people are there?

Probably over a hundred.

Are your tribe's annual activities like this?

Yes,

The sea buckthorn is not white yet.
 Don't say white, I should say red. (Laughter)
 Pray for merit to reach the hungry ghosts and those suffering
 from hunger and thirst.
 May all beings from whom we have taken life for their blood
 and meat be reborn in the pure land through the power
 of the compassionate Buddha's mantra
 Pray for all beings not to suffer from generation to generation.
 Flowers bloom there.
 Did you get cold?
 No.
 Let's go.
 Footsteps.
 Chorus of the compassionate Buddha's mantra.
 Put it there. Don't scatter garbage, take it back.
 Cars.
 Ringing bell.
 The spiritual song of the compassionate Buddha's mantra.

ལ་བད།
 མྱིས་པའི་རྟོག་ཟླ།
 ཏུང་ཟླ།
 འདི་ནས་མྱེན་ལ་འགོ།
 གཏུལ་བཞག་ཡོད་ཀི
 དེའི་ནང་ལ་གཏུལ་ཨེ་ཡོད་ཀི།
 ཀན་ནང་ལ་གཏུལ་ཨེ་ཡོད་ཀི།
 མི་འཁྲིགས་པ་དང་ལྷན་རིས་གཞིགས་ཀྱི་གཟུངས་ཟུགས་འདོན་པ།
 ལྷོན་ལ་ཐོན་ནས་ཤོག་མར་གཤོག་པ་ཐོགས་འདུག
 མ་ཉི་ཐོན།
 འགོ་ཕུ་བོ།
 ལྷར་བུ་ལ་བཟང་དན་ཡོད་ཀི།
 ཤོག་མ་ཟེར་བ་དེ་མ་འདྲ་བ་ཡིན་ནི་རེད།
 མི་འཁྲིགས་པ་དང་ལྷན་རིས་གཞིགས་ཀྱི་གཟུངས་ཟུགས་འདོན་པ།
 མ་ཉི་མགུར་དབྱངས།
 གཞུག་ནས་ལྷིད་གཉིས་ཡོང་ན་འདི་བཞིན་གཏུལ་དགོས་ནི་རེད་ཀོ།
 འོ་ཡ།

ནང་སོན་རྗེས། ཨ་གོ་ཐལ།

གོ་ཐལ།

འུར་བརྒྱལ་ན་རྟོག་མ་ཐེ་མང་ལ་བྱད་འགྲོ་གི།

མཐའ་ཁར་གཏོ་ལ།

མང་པོ་མ་གཏུ་ལ།

མགོར་མ་གཏུ་ལ། འདི་ཀར་གཏོ་ལ།

འདི་ན་རྟོག་མ་ཅི་ཙམ་ཡོད་ན།

ཏུ་ལྟ་.....

རྒྱ་ཀུའི་ཐལ་ན་བཟང་ཟེར་གྱི་དོ་རྒྱལ་ཚང་གིས།

མཁའ་པོ་རྩལ་ཁྲིམས་རྒྱ་མཚོ་ཚང་གིས་རྒྱ་ཀུའི་མི་བཟང་ཟེར།

གཞན་གྱི་སྐྱེ་མ་ཅི་ཅོག་དང་རང་གི་སྐྱེ་མ་སྐྱེན་ཅོག་ཟེར་ནི་རེད།

ཏུ་ལྟ་.....

གོག་ཚང་དུ་ལ་སྦྱིན་པ་བཏང་སོང་།

ལ་ཡངས་ལེན་དགོས།

པ་ལོ་གོག་སྦྱིན། བ.....ངས་ཏུ་ཟེར་རྒྱ་ཡིན།

དེ་ན་སྤང་མ་ནག་པོ་ཞིག་ཡོད་ཀྱི། །མ།

མགོན་པོ་བྲག་ནག་ལ་བསང་གཏོང་གི་སོང་ནས་པེད་ཚོ།

ཨ་རོགས་ཚོ། ཅམ་པ་ཚར་སོང་ནི་ཡོད་ན་ཤོག་ར། ལྟེར་ཡ།

ལུ་ནག་ཁྲོས་བཟང་ནས་སྤོང། གང་འཇུང་བསམ་ན་འཇུང།

དུང་འབྱད་པ།

འདི་ལྟར་ལྷག་དགོས། མ་ཐེ་འདོན་པ།

གོག་སྦྱིན་གཏོང་གི་ཡོང་ནས། གོག་ཚང་དེའི་ནང་ལ་སྐྱགས་དང་།

ཉི་ཤུ་ལྷན་ཅུ་ཞིག་ཡིན། ལྟར་བུ་ལུས་ཡ། ད་ལྟར་བུ་ལུས།

ལྟར་བུ་རྒྱ་གོ་དམར་ནག་ཞིག་རེད།

ལྟར་ཚར་བཏོག་མི་ཉན།

དེ་རིང་གོག་སྦྱིན་གཏོང་ནི་ཨེ་མང་གི།

མང་གི། པལ་ཚར་མི་ཅི་ཙམ་ཡོད་ལ།

པལ་ཚར་མི་བརྒྱའི་ཡར་ནང་ན་ཡོད་ཀྱི་རེད་པ།

ཁྲོད་ཚོའི་ལོ་རེ་རེ་བཏང་ནི་ཨེ་ཡིན།

འོ་ཡ།

ལྟར་བུ་དུང་དུང་དཀར་པོའི་ཅིག་སོང་མེད་ཀྱི། །དམར་པོ་མ་རེད་ནས། དཀར་པོ་རྒྱག་པོ། །དགོད་སྐྱ།

བསེ་རག་ཡི་དགས་བཀའ་སྐྱོམ་སྤང་གི་ཡོད་ནི་དག་གི་དགེ་རྒྱ་ཆེན་པོ་ཞིག་ཐོབ་ནས་སྐྱོན་ལས།

སྐྱོ་མ་ཐེ་པེད་རྩི་རྩི་རྩི་རྩི།

ཤ་ལྷག་ཟས་བའི་དུང་འགོ་མ་ལུས་པ། །གསུང་ཡི་གེ་དུག་མའི་བྱིན་རྒྱབས་ཀྱིས། །ཞིང་བདེ་བ་ཅན་དུ་སྦྱེ་བར་ཤོག

སྦྱེ་བ་ནས་སྦྱེ་བ། ཚོ་རབས་ནས་ཚོ་རབས་ཐམས་ཅད་དུ་རྒྱུ་རྒྱུན་ཞིག་མི་སྤོང་ནས་སྐྱོན་ལས།

མེ་ཏོག་ལག་དུས་ད་སྤོང་བཟང་ཡོད་ནི་རེད།

ཨ་གང་ཐལ། འུན། མ་གང་ཐལ།
འུ་གཉིས་ཀ་འགོ།
དོག་གླུ།
ལྷན་རིས་གཟིགས་ཀྱི་གཟུངས་བགང་བ།
དེ་ལྷངས་ནས་ཕར་འཕེན་རོགས།
གང་སྟེགས་མ་འཕེན་ལྱིར་ལ་ལྱེར་སོང་།
ལྷངས་འཁོར་གྱི་གླུ།
འི་ལ་ལྷ་དཀོལ་བའི་གླུ།

SHEEP SHEARING 2023 IN RGYAB LUNG
(JIALONG) COMMUNITY, RTA NAG MA
(HEIMAHE) TOWNSHIP TOWN, GSER CHEN
(GONGHE) COUNTY, MTSHO LHO (HAINAN)
TIBETAN AUTONOMOUS PREFECTURE,
MTSHO SNGON (QINGHAI)
PROVINCE, PR CHINA¹

Sgrol ma yag ལྷོ་མ་ཡག། (Zhuo ma you 卓玛优)

11 minutes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10130698>

May-June is sheep-shearing time in my home area of Rgyab lung (Jialong) Community, Rta nag ma (Heimahe) Township Town, Gser chen (Gonghe) County,² Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. My family stopped shearing sheep in about 2007. I filmed

¹ Sgrol ma yag ལྷོ་མ་ཡག། 2025. Sheep Shearing 2023 in Rgyab lung (Jialong) Community, Rta nag ma (Heimahe) Township Town, Gser chen (Gonghe) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:286-290.

² In 2021, Gser chen County included seven towns, four townships, ninety-nine administrative communities, and a total population of 133,409. The county had twenty-two ethnic minorities (seventy percent of the total population) including Tibetans, Hui (8,844), and Mongolians (2,140). Han numbered 34,364. The county had 18,761,600 *mu* of usable grassland, 457,600 *mu* of arable land, and an average altitude of 3,200 <https://bit.ly/3Gw2RfS> 20 November 2022). Heimahe's (township town) population was 4,000 with Tibetans accounting for ninety percent of the total. The township town is 1,000 square kilometers in area with jurisdiction over Rgyab lung (Jialong), Brag mchog (Zhiheq), Bum pa (Wenba), and Ra 'khyog (Ranheq) <https://bit.ly/3GuaDXK> 20 November 2022). The 2011 population of Mtsho lho Prefecture was 437,800, including 269,100 Tibetans (sixty-three percent, <https://bit.ly/2OAGwll> 25 July 2020).

the first time I participated in sheep shearing since then, helping five local families shear sheep. There have been many changes in sheep-shearing, including what families do with the sheared wool and shearing tools. Most families have around ten helpers.

Father (b. 1970) said that if we don't shear at this time, the sheep will be uncomfortable, scratch against walls, rocks, and ditches, roll over, be unable to stand, and die.

At around five p.m., my cousin's family arrived with their sheep, brought from the summer pasture to the spring pasture. After the family drove the sheep into the sheep enclosure, the son slaughtered a sheep, and his parents went to the township town by motorcycle and bought various beverages, fruit, biscuits, and other items. Father helped the son take care of the meat.

Early the next morning, after a simple breakfast, the family got up at four and began shearing. Later, helpers came one after another.

Before shearing, men sharpen the *bal he* 'shears', and two or three family women prepare milk tea and cook meat and noodles. Each man has ten *bkyig tigs* 'strings', indicating each is to catch ten sheep and shear them. This is *bkyigs thabs gcig* 'one round'. If it is a shearer's first time to shear, other men help him.

When I was a child, each man had his own strings, and most were made of wool. They colored their strings to differentiate them from others. Father's strings were wool and colored red on top. Every time he finished shearing, I was responsible for collecting the strings. At that time, men twisted their strings around their waists and pulled one when they caught a sheep and tied its legs.

Most men who participated in the sheep shearing this year had few wool strings. Instead, they bought cloth from the market and tore it into strips.

During shearing, two or three women were responsible for marking the sheared sheep with *lcags rtsi* 'paint'. Each family had a distinctive paint color and marked the sheep differently. For instance, the first family I helped used green on the neck and blue on the rump. Other women or children were

responsible for collecting *bal rdul* 'pieces of wool that had broken off during shearing'. When I was a child, we were responsible for collecting *bal rdul* and preventing the sheep from escaping as elders were catching them. I did the same during the sheep shearing this year.

After one round finished, the men collected their strings and took a short break. Some resharpenered their scissors, and the family offered beverages and snacks.

An element of fun in sheep shearing is young men competing to see who is the fastest. They joke with each other. One of my cousins was the funniest person that day. He teased young men that they would not find good wives if they didn't shear the wool well. The young men also verbally sparred with each other. One of my cousins and his friend had a contest of to see who could shear the fastest. My cousin lost several times, so his friends and cousins teased him that he might not find a good wife. They also teasingly suggested that he join more sheep shearing events to practice his ability.

Father said that when he was young, they were happy to join the sheep-shearing events of local families. Once, one of his cousins and he participated in sheep shearing. There were many young men there to help the family, and they competed to see who was the fastest. Father laughingly said that one young man had sheared the edge of his robe that day. Everybody laughed at him and teased him that day. Jokes and laughing release tiredness.

Some families medicate the sheep during the shearing because they won't have to catch them again with a few family members. For instance, one family brought anthrax vaccine provided by the local government.

One family traditionally takes care of the wool. Women scatter the sheared wool on the ground in a line near the sheep enclosure and spread other wool on the scattered wool. A woman puts a stick on the scattered wool and twists it. Another woman helps her twist the scattered wool. After twisting it tightly, they make a line of twisted wool into a round shape.

Two or three women spin several pieces of wool to make long strips men use to bind the *bal dos* 'rounded wool' with a *yog thag* 'spun strip'. This final process is locally called *bal gcu sdom byed pa*. Men put the *bal dos* in the family's storage room.

Very few families take care of the wool in traditional ways. The shorn wool is placed into plastic bags, which does not involve arduous labor, such as the last family event I joined. They made long strips, scattered the wool on the ground, and so forth.

Finally, the family offers water for the men to wash their hands. The housewife and the husband or other family members ask others to sit. They offer tea, meat, noodles, bread, snacks, and various beverages, repeatedly urging guests and helpers to eat and drink more. If some are unfamiliar with the guests, they do not eat much, pretending they are full after a small amount of food.

I did the same in one family where I met some guests for the first time. The family leader is a relative of my father and has no son. He is in his seventies, so my Father helps him yearly during their sheep-shearing.

This was my first time participating in this family's sheep-shearing. The day before the shearing, the family head phoned Father and asked if he could help. He said it was fine if he could not because of Father's back pain. Father said he would help and would bring me with him. The man was grateful for Father's generous help.

Father is famous for his sheep-shearing ability. Locals said Father was the best shearer in our community when he was young.

Except for the last family, Father didn't join the sheep-shearing of the other families that I joined. Many helpers said it was fine that he did not help because they knew about his back pain. Some helpers said that the work would be easier if Father were there.

Father said sheep-shearing took place in the summer pasture when he was younger because there were few families, few livestock, enough grass for the animals, and locals moved to

the summer pasture earlier. So, they packed the *bal dos* on yaks to the spring pasture where they could store the *bal dos* as long as they wanted.

TIBETAN TERMS

bal dos བལ་དོས།

bal gcu sdom byed pa བལ་གཅུ་སྐོམ་བྱེད་པ།

bal he བལ་ཧེ།

bal rdul བལ་རདུལ།

bkyig thag བརྒྱུག་ཐག།

bkyigs thabs gcig བརྒྱུགས་ཐབས་གཅིག།

gser chen གསེར་ཆེན།

lcags rtsi ལུགས་རྩི།

mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྒོན།

rgyab lung རྒྱལ་ལུང་།

rta nag ma ཏ་ནག་མ།

sgrol ma yag སྐྱལ་མ་ཡག།

yog thag ཡོག་ཐག།

CHINESE TERMS

Jialong 加隆

Heimahe 黑马河

Hainan 海南

Gonghe 共和

A MDO TIBETAN MILKING, CHURNING BUTTER, AND WEAVING¹

Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཐོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措)

15 minutes 38 seconds

https://archive.org/details/karens-film-3_202311

On Friday, 1 September 2023, I used an iPhone 12 Pro Max to capture footage of my mother, Rgya kho (b. 1964), milking, churning butter, washing wool, and weaving at our home in Sha rgya Community, Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho Lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho snon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

Rgya kho is a single mother of four daughters. She lived with her grandmother until her passing. Afterward, she lived with her mother. Her education was cut short in the second grade by her grandmother, who believed girls should stay at home to care for the elderly, give birth, and raise children. This idea also applied to my two older sisters. Nevertheless, my mother has not forgotten the Tibetan alphabet taught by her teacher and is currently self-learning Tibetan to read textbooks and WeChat messages.

My mother and I have breakfast at eight a.m. and begin milking our seven female yaks at eight-thirty, which takes about thirty minutes. On the day I recorded, it took forty minutes due to rainy weather.

My mother prefers the traditional method of churning butter, citing the time-saving benefits, as she does not need to churn it daily. In summer, she churns butter once every three days and once a week in autumn and winter. Despite suggestions

¹ Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཐོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措). 2025. A mdo mdo Tibetan Milking, Churning Butter, and Weaving. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:291-292.

from villagers to switch to a machine churn, she continues with the traditional method, valuing the superior taste and health benefits of handmade butter. It takes at least two hours to churn butter the old-fashioned way. My mother begins churning at one p.m. and continues until three p.m. My sister-in-law and I assisted her, which is not in the film. I eagerly anticipated these days in my childhood, as Mother would share butter balls, my favorite, with me and the neighboring children, to our delight.

Mother wove only during my primary school years. During that period, women from our neighborhood collaborated to weave and create black tent material. However, with the contemporary preference for white tents due to convenience and warmth, I haven't seen Mother weaving since I started high school. Recently, when I asked for a handmade bag, Mother agreed to make one for me, which I videoed.

TIBETAN TERMS

gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།
mang zdong མང་རྫོང་།
mgo mang མགོ་མང་།
mstho lho མཚོ་ལྗོ།
mstho snon མཚོ་སྐོན།
rgaya kho ལྷ་ལོ།
sha rgya ག་རྒྱ།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南
Guomaying 过马营
Hainan 海南
Qinghai 青海

GRANDMA'S (DKAR MO RGYAL, B. 1937) TIBETAN SNUFF¹

Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措)

8 minutes 54 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15128342>

I used an iPhone 12 on Sunday, 2 February 2025, to record my maternal grandmother (Dkar mo rgyal, b. 1937) in Sha rgya Community, Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China, as she made snuff.

My grandmother began taking snuff when she was around twenty. She and my mom (Rgya kho, b. 1964) are snuff addicts. No matter how busy they are, they find time for snuff, which they take before breakfast. My younger sister (Klum mo mtsho, b. 2006) often complains about this. They take snuff wherever they go, just as modern youth always use their mobile phones.

Three stores sell snuff in our county town, but they don't specialize in it. One sells children's clothes, another sells prayer flags, and the third is a private Tibetan medicine hospital.

A pack of snuff cost twenty RMB in 2025. It cost five RMB when I was in primary school.

One day last year, my grandma asked me to buy snuff. Unfortunately, the county stores had no snuff in stock that day. A middle-aged woman who owned the store said few people buy snuff today.

My mother bought snuff in Xining City. I don't know where else she bought it. The owner of another store in the

¹ Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措). 2025. Grandma's (Dkar mo rgyal, b. 1937) Tibetan Snuff. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:293-294.

county town said they occasionally had snuff, but they were out of stock when I asked. They added that they would have some in a few days.

After I returned home, I told Grandmother what they said. She worried they wouldn't be able to get snuff in the future. She said, "What if there is no snuff left?"

When their snuff was running out, my mother went to town and bought at least five packages each time.

I wanted to record Grandmother making snuff after I read an article about Fentanyl by an author who interviewed three Fentanyl addicts. Even though my grandmother and mom say snuff is beneficial, there are also negatives, such as their poor sense of smell. For example, one day, I heard my sister complaining that my mother and grandma were smoking snuff.

She said, "I asked you to take less snuff. You won't be able to smell spoiled food."

That day, Sister smelled a foul odor and found a piece of spoiled bread. Grandma and Mom didn't smell it. Also, during this winter vacation, I bought perfume and asked my mom, "Does it smell nice?"

She smiled and said, "I can't smell it."

TIBETAN TERMS

CHINESE TERMS

dkar mo rgyal དཀར་མོ་རྒྱལ།
gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།
klum mo mtsho ལུ་མོ་མཚོ།
mang zdong མང་རྫོང།
mgo mang མགོ་མང།
mstho lho མཚོ་ལྗོ།
mstho snon མཚོ་སྐོན།
rgaya kho རྒྱལ་མོ།
sha rgya ཤ་རྒྱ།

Guinan 贵南
Guoma Ying 过马营
Hainan 海南
Qinghai 青海

MOM'S TIBETAN CAKES – HOMEMADE DELIGHTS¹

Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措)

5 minutes 40 seconds

<https://zenodo.org/records/15128324>

On Wednesday, 12 February 2025, I recorded my mother (Rgya kho, b. 1964) in Sha rgya Community, Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China, making Tibetan cakes. I used an iPhone 12 to film.

As the Tibetan New Year (Lo sar) approaches, local women busily make small Tibetan cakes as gifts for guests. Since childhood, I vividly remember my mother making Tibetan cakes and helping neighbors with the task. Around Lo sar, all the local women make bread and Tibetan cakes. They always cooperate and assist one another, which is a heartwarming tradition.

However, in recent years, my neighbors have started to buy bread and Tibetan cakes from the township town. They consider this to be more convenient. One kilogram of wild yams cost eighty-five RMB in 2025. Combined with other ingredients, the cost is almost the same as purchasing finished products from the store. So, in terms of price, making them at home and buying them is comparable.

My mother mentioned that when she mashed wild yams and cheese in the past, she used a stone mill. The stone mill was inconvenient, and the mashed wild yams didn't turn out well. Although my mother makes Tibetan cakes almost yearly, I had never paid much attention to the process. These traditional foods

¹ Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措). 2025. Mom's Tibetan Cakes – Homemade Delights. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:295-296.

and practices are significant, so I asked my mother to show me how to make Tibetan cakes.

TIBETAN TERMS

gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།

mang zdong མང་རྫོང་།

mgo mang མགོ་མང་།

mstho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

mstho snon མཚོ་སྐྱོན།

rgaya kho རྒྱ་ལོ།

sha rgya ག་རྒྱ།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南

Guomaying 过马营

Hainan 海南

Qinghai 青海

THE FIRST DAY OF THE TIBETAN NEW YEAR (2025):
MTSHAMS THOG GONG MA MONASTERY¹

Sngags sa khon thar rgyal སྔགས་ས་ཁོན་ཐར་རྒྱལ།
(Ehesa Kantaijia 俄合萨侃太加)

6 minutes 59 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15042927>

Camera: iPhone12

Date: 29 January 2025

Mtshams thog gong ma Monastery, where I made this film, is located in Nyig ldang (Niudang) Community, 'Brong thu (Zhongtie) Township, Brag dkar (Xinghai) County, Mstho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

My family got up at five a.m. on the first day of Tibetan Lo sar (the first day of the first Tibetan lunar month). The men in my family prepared to visit the *bla ma* and monks in Mtshams thog gong ma Monastery.

After my mother prepared *bsang* 'incense offerings', the men performed a fire offering. My father and I chanted an offering scripture.

Meanwhile, my mother made breakfast of barley flour and milk tea, which we had together.

My father, my two brothers, and I then went to the monastery by car wearing our Tibetan robes. We needed to arrive early because of Zhal gser, which was held before nine a.m.

We left the car in the monastery parking lot.

¹ Sngags sa khon thar rgyal སྔགས་ས་ཁོན་ཐར་རྒྱལ། (Ehesa Kantaijia 俄合萨侃太加). 2025. The First Day of the Tibetan New Year (2025): Mtshams thog gong ma Monastery. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:297-300.

Conversation One:

Monks: There are visitors.

Skal bzang: I will wait for you, brother.

My brother (Dpa' rgyal): OK.

Yum skaybs: Haha... he said OK.

Dpa' rgyal: I just saw someone pinned to the ground by monks,
and it disappointed me. I thought it was not you. Haha...

Mtshan bzang: What an intense day!

Monks: Come here. Take the bag of barley flour.

Mtshan bzang: Did you get the bag of barley flour?

Lha brtan: Yes, but they took it back. If we try here, we will
definitely get it.

Conversation Two:

Monks: Let me try. Give me one bag.

Monk: Thank you all very much. Longlife. Thanks. Bkra shis
bde legs!

Conversation Three:

Monks: This is very good for you. I wish you become wealthy,
haha....

Monk: Really good.

Monk: May you live to be 108 years old. Longlife.

Monk: Thanks.

Monks: Let's go.

Dialogue Four:

Child: Wow, they're coming. Dad, let me go.

Monks: Happy New Year.

Visitors: Happy New Year.

Monks: Rub, rub more.

Monks: It's enough. Stop.

Monks: Everybody, come here. Rub more.

Dialogue Five:

Monks and visitors: Come on, come on...

Dialogue Six:

Monk: Get the bag of barley flour back. Grab your own bag.

Monks: Have you got the bag of barley flour

Monk: Yes, I got it.

Father: Hi. Should we go back?

Me: Wait a moment.

Dialogue Seven:

Me: Wow! Too much gold.

On this day, as long as there are no life-threatening problems like disease in the village, the New Year is celebrated. Monks rub guests' faces with barley flour in a ritual called *Zhal gser 'bul ba* 'face painted with gold'. It is only held once a year on this morning. Villagers consider the 'gold' of this day to be very precious. It gives confidence and belief to overcome setbacks and live a happy life. Visitors can also grab *rtsam khug* 'barley flour bags' from monks and keep the flour inside. The bag can also be used to contain incense offering materials. The barley flour is spread on *lhas ra* 'livestock areas' to suppress livestock illness.

People use *rtsam pa* partly because of its white color. The main monastery's sacred mage is *Thug rje chen po* 'Avalokiteshvara', who has fair skin. *Rtsam pa*'s color is the same as *Thug rje chen po*, so people believe *rtsam pa* can help them have a happy life, similar to a ritual in which people paint the Buddha gold in *Lha sa*. The ritual suggests auspiciousness and perfection.

TIBETAN TERMS

bkra shis bde legs བགྲ་ཤེས་བདེ་ལེགས། Good luck!

bla ma ལྷ་མ། spiritual teacher

bsang བསང། incense offerings

gser གཤེན། gold, symbolized by rtsam pa 'roasted barley flour'

lhas ra ལྷ་ས་ར། livestock areas

lo sar ལོ་སར། Tibetan New Year, the first day of the first Tibetan lunar month

lo sar bzang ལོ་སར་བཟང། Happy New Year

mtshams thog gong ma མཚམས་ཐོག་གོང་མ། མཚམས་ཐོག་གོང་མའམ་བགྲ་ཤེས་ཚོས་རྫོང་དགེ་འཕེལ་བྱང་ཆུབ་སྐོང། Upper Anchorite Monastery is in Nyig ldang Community, Brag dkar County, Mtsho lhu Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon Province, China. Mtshams thog gong ma was built on Lha ri zhal dkar Mountain and is known as Bkra shis chos rzdong dge 'pel byang chub gling. It was founded by Snags sa dge bshes 'jam dbyang don yod in 1912.

nyig ldang ཉིག་ལྗང། The Tibetan village where the film was made.

rtsam khug རྩ་ཁུག་ barley flour bag

rtsam pa རྩ་པ། roasted barley flour

sku tshe ring སྐུ་ཚེ་རིང། longlife

thug rje chen po ཐུག་རྗེ་ཆེན་པོ། Lord of Great Compassion (Avalokiteshvara), with 1,000 hands and eyes, and fair skin

zhal gser 'bul ba རྩལ་གསེར་འབྲུལ་བ། face painted with gold

CHINESE TERMS

Ehesa Kantaijia 俄合萨侃太加

Hainan 海南

Niudang 牛当

Qinghai 青海

Xinghai 兴海

Zhongtie 中铁

YAK PARASITE INJECTABLES: BDE SKYID (XINGFU),
MGO MANG (GUOMAYING) TOWNSHIP, MANG
RDZONG (GUINAN) COUNTY, MSTHO LHO (HAINAN)
TIBETAN AUTONOMOUS PREFECTURE, MSTHO
SNGON (QINGHAI) PROVINCE, PR CHINA¹
Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措)

6 minutes 35 seconds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11103648>

On Tuesday, 24 March 2024, I visited my older sister's home in Bde skyid (Xingfu), Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China, which required approximately thirty-five minutes from my home by private car. My sister, Ma rdo (b. 1984), married Rta lo rgyal (b. 1978) when she was seventeen in an arranged marriage. They have two daughters and a son.

Rta lo rgyal informed me that he administered medication to the yaks to treat parasites, but the parasites returned in a week. Recently, a veterinarian informed him about anti-parasite injectables that offered three months of protection. Thus, he planned to go to town the next day to obtain the injectables.

Sister and I led the yaks into an enclosure on government-owned land. The government allows herders to graze their livestock on this land after harvest. Most herders use this land because they can do so without paying, but only in winter and early autumn. The land is a fifteen-minute walk from their homes.

¹ Gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ། (Saimaocuo 赛毛措). 2025. Yak Parasite Injectables: Bde skyid (Xingfu), Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:301-302.

On Monday, 25 March 2024, at five a.m., Rta lo rgyal went to town to get the injectables, which took forty minutes from his home by private car. He returned at nine a.m. We started administering the injectables at nine-thirty a.m. Neighbors assisted. It took two hours to treat one hundred yaks.

TIBETAN TERMS

bde skyid བདེ་སྐྱིད།
gser mo mtho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།
ma rdo མ་རྩོ།
mang zdong མང་རྫོང་།
mgo mang མགོ་མང་།
mstho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
mstho snon མཚོ་སྐོན།
rgaya kho ལྷོ་ལོ།
rta lo rgyal ལྷོ་ལོ་རྒྱལ།
sha rgya ཤ་རྒྱ།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南
Guomaying 过马营
Hainan 海南
Qinghai 青海
Xingfu 幸福

MAKING GRO KHRA BREAD FOR TIBETAN NEW YEAR (2024): 'BA' DGON TOWNSHIP, CHU DMAR LEG COUNTY, MTSHO SNGON PROVINCE, PR CHINA¹

Bkra shis rab rgyas (Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰)

1 minute 31 seconds

<https://zenodo.org/records/15354291>

I am Bkra shis rab rgyas (b. 1997). My mother (Zla ba bzang mo, b. 1972) makes *gro khra* for Lo sar 'Tibetan New Year'. *Gro khra* comes in two colors - brown and white. The brown part is made in two ways. One involves boiling tea, removing the tea leaves, and adding flour to the tea water. The second is to add black sugar to water and mix flour with it. After preparing the brown and white dough separately, Mother rolled them out on a chopping board. She twisted the two doughs together, cut them into pieces, and deep-fried them in vegetable oil.

Filmed in Thang skyid Village, 'Ba' dgon (Bagan) Township, Chu dmar leb (Qumalai) County, Yul shul (Yushu) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China by Bkra shis rab rgyas in 2024 at his home.

TIBETAN TERMS

'ba' dgon འབའ་དགོན།

རྒྱལ།

chu dmar leg རྒྱ་དམར་ལེག།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྡོད།

yul shul ཡུལ་ཤུལ།

bkra shis rab rgyas བཟླ་ཤེས་རབ་

gro khra རྒྱ་ལ།

thang skyid ཐང་སྐྱིད།

zla ba bzang mo ལྷ་བ་བཟང་མོ།

¹ Bkra shis rab rgyas (Zhaxirangjie 扎西让杰). 2025. Making *Gro khra* Bread for Tibetan New Year (2024): 'Ba' dgon Township, Chu dmar leg County, Mtsho sngon Province, PR China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 65:303.